

THE NEW CONSTITUTION OF UZBEKISTAN AND "STRATEGY-
2030"

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Abstract: The article briefly discusses the changes in the new constitution of Uzbekistan and the goals set in the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy of the President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev.

Key words: Constitution, Uzbekistan, strategy, document, reform

It can be said that the new version of the Constitution, signed by the head of our state on September 11 of this year, served as the basis for the decree "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030" and the decision "On measures to implement the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030 in 2023 in a timely manner" . After all, it is no coincidence that in the preamble of the decree, it is emphasized that "in the updated constitutional and legal conditions, it is required to improve the main directions of the development of our country and bring the implemented large-scale reforms to a new stage." As a result, it was noted that realizing the desire of our compatriots to build a new Uzbekistan, raising a healthy, educated and morally mature generation, forming a strong economy, guaranteeing justice, rule of law, security and stability is set as a priority goal.

At this point, let's recall the speeches of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 78th session of the United Nations General Assembly on September 19, 2023:

"In our Basic Law, we reaffirmed our commitment to the principles of equality of all citizens, human rights, freedom of speech and conscience, regardless of nationality, language and religion.

We adopted the "Uzbekistan-2030" development strategy on this legal basis. This strategy is in line with the "Sustainable Development Goals" of the United Nations, and we are fully and firmly fulfilling all our commitments.

It is known that "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy includes 100 important goals in 5 priority directions, and this document was developed based on the results of the gained experience, international expertise and public discussion.

On the other hand, the decision on measures to implement the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy in 2023 in a high-quality and timely manner, adopted by the head of our state, aims to ensure the high-quality and timely implementation of this document in the "Year of attention to people and quality education". In all directions defined in the strategy, the interests of the population, that is, the people and the country, were put first.

In particular, Chapter IV of the Strategy was devoted to the direction "Ensuring the rule of law, organizing public administration in the service of the people". It includes 51 practical measures and 21 tasks within the framework of 16 goals (goals 74-89) in this area. It is envisaged to develop 41 target indicators related to neighborhood, local state bodies, representative bodies, civil service, civil society institutions, judiciary, human rights, advocacy, corruption issues and prepare 25 normative legal documents. In particular, a number of tasks were defined in the items such as "Reforms on the organization of public administration and improvement of public administration" and "Ensuring the rule of law and reforms in the judicial system":

- Increase the share of public services provided in electronic form to 100%;
- A new stage of the "Electronic Government" system - transitioning to the "Digital Government" system and ensuring that all documents and relations are in digital form;
- Abolition of excessive formal procedures, such as writing an application, filling out various forms, and creating a system where government agencies receive the necessary documents from the electronic database.

In short, the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy is an important document that defines not only the next seven-year development of our country, but also its long-term development strategy. There is no doubt that timely implementation of the goals set in it will serve as an important factor in the rapid development of the state and society in all aspects.

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